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Abstract

This document represents a deliverable communication by the EJP SOIL internal project 'MINOTAUR' about quantified relationships between soil biodiversity and soil functions. Using literature review data and collected data in MINOTAUR for biological indicators frequently used in soil monitoring and soil health assessment studies, the objective of this document is to provide some elaborated examples of EPFs. In this document, results include four examples of mediation by various groups of soil organisms of soil processes that critically contribute to the provision of some essential ecosystem services: primary productivity, soil structure maintenance assessed by soil aggregate stability, water regulation assessed by water infiltration and carbon storage. While the MINOTAUR project has closed to date, it is the ambition of the authors to publish the results of this particular study in a peer-reviewed journal. This has already been done for one ecosystem service (primary production), but not for the others. As such publication would appear under its own DOI, the raw data used in the analyses will be published as supplementary information in the journal, and to avoid further duplication are not available in association to this Zenodo deposited document. When published, the DOI of the paper will be provided here in an update.

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1. Introduction

Soil organisms through their functions such as carbon transformation, nutrient cycling, soil structure maintenance and biological population regulation, collectively contribute to a variety of soil-based goods and services (Kibblewhite et al., 2008). While a large number of studies have focused on the link between soil organisms and functions, the quantitative link between functions and indicators, and more specifically biological indicators, is still poorly understood, mainly due to the complexity of the soil ecosystem (Cousin et al., 2024). However, such relationships, commonly known as ‘pedotransfer functions’ or, more to the point here, ‘ecological production functions’ (EPFs), can help to model and predict the potential delivery of ecosystem services on the basis of environmental survey data (Faber et al. 2021). In view of the recently proposed EU Soil Monitoring and Resilience Law (EC 2023), these EPFs may be applied in soil health assessments aimed to evaluate the (potential) provision of some essential ecosystem services, and may serve to inspire further development of comparable mathematical tools to this purpose.

In this context, the objective of this document is to provide some elaborated examples of EPFs using literature review data and collected data in MINOTAUR for biological indicators frequently used in soil monitoring and soil health assessment studies. We have focused our attention on four essential ecosystem services: plant productivity, soil structure maintenance (assessed by soil aggregate stability), water regulation (assessed by water infiltration), both of which are strongly related to soil erosion risk, and carbon storage. Indeed, these four ecosystem services are very important for agricultural soils, and appear major in a context of climate change and agro-ecological transition.

2. Primary productivity

The results of this study have already been published (Romero et al., 2024). In order to assess the link between soil health, primary productivity and soil organisms, a study was conducted using LUCAS soil monitoring data covering 588 sites from 27 European countries in three major land-uses: forests (also called woodland) (n=185), grasslands (n=126) and arable lands (also called crop lands) (n=277). Primary productivity was assessed by the fraction of absorbed photosynthetically active radiation (FAPAR) derived from remote sensing data obtained from each of the 588 sampling locations. Soil health was established as a composite index built from seven soil properties including chemical (soil organic carbon, phosphorus content), physical (water infiltration potential) and biotic factors, focusing on microbial component (microbial biomass, the richness of N-fixing bacteria, the richness of mycorrhizal (arbuscular and ectomycorrhizal) fungi and plant disease control).

Results: This study showed that soil health was higher in woodlands than in grasslands and croplands (respectively 31.4 % and 76.1% higher), and that soil health was positively linked to primary productivity in grasslands and arable lands but not in forest.

Random Forest analyses were performed to evaluate and rank bacterial and fungal taxa by their capacity to predict plant productivity (figure 1).

Figure 1: Relative importance of main predictors (top ten) for primary productivity. a–c, Results are based on random forest analysis in croplands (a, n = 277), grasslands (b, n = 126) and woodlands (c, n = 185). Dark colours indicate positive predictor effects on primary productivity and light colours indicate negative effects. Variance explained by models is indicated as percentage (%). Asterisks indicate a significant effect based on averaged model coefficients following permutation testing with 1,000 permutations (*** $P < 0.001$, ** $P < 0.010$, * $P < 0.050$) (Romero et al., 2024)

Moreover, structural equation model (SEM) analysis were done to analyze and describe the effect of soil biodiversity on primary production (Figure 2).

Figure 2: SEM describing direct and indirect effects of climate, edaphic factors and soil biodiversity on primary productivity across different land-use types. a, Croplands. b, Grasslands. c, Woodlands. The proportion of explained variance (R²) in primary productivity is indicated for each model. Goodness-of-fit statistics are also included. Dashed lines indicate that none of the variables included was significant (P > 0.05). Variables included within 'Edaphic factors' are pH, clay content (C), soil organic carbon (OC), phosphorus content (P), soil bulk density (BD) and microbial biomass (MB). Variables included within 'Climatic factors' are monthly air temperature (T) and monthly precipitation (P). Variables included within 'Soil biodiversity' are Acidobacteria (Aci), Actinobacteria (Act), Mortierellomycota (Mor), Verrucomicrobia (Ver), Firmicutes (Fir), Nitrospirae (Nit), Chytridiomycota (Chy), Mucoromycota (Muc), Ascomycota (Asc), Basidiomycota (Bas), Proteobacteria (Pro), N-fixing bacteria (Nfix), Mycorrhiza (Myc) and plant pathogens (Pat). AIC, Akaike information criterion; PP, primary productivity (Romeo et al, 2024).

The study showed that the main biological predictors of productivity differ according to the land use. In forest-woodland, Firmicutes and more broadly microbial biomass are good predictors. In cropland, the richness of Acidobacteria, Firmicutes and Proteobacteria are positively associated to primary productivity, while Actinobacteria is negatively associated. In grassland, Proteobacteria appears again a good predictor of productivity, in addition to Mycorrhiza. In both grassland and cropland, primary productivity is negatively related to plant pathogens (Tableau 3).

In synthesis, using LUCAS soil monitoring data, plant productivity in grassland, arable land and forest soils was shown to be positively related to soil health as indexed by a combination of a number of indicators for microbial community composition and physical and chemical parameters. The Random Forest analyses which evaluated and ranked bacterial and fungal taxa by their capacity to predict plant productivity, identified some bacterial groups as best predictors in arable land crop productivity (where both positive and negative correlations exist), whereas fungal taxa (including pathogenic species) performed better for grassland productivity. Higher microbial taxonomic richness diversity did not always enhance productivity, as arable soils hosted higher taxonomic richness but also harboured a greater numbers of pathogens.

3. Soil structure maintenance – aggregate stability

Soil structural stability is a key indicator of soil health, particularly its resistance to erosion caused by wind and rain (Le Bissonnais, 1996). It is assessed by studying aggregate stability, which depends on various physical, chemical, and biological factors, whether internal (specific to the soil) or external (dependent on climate and land use) (Amézqueta, 1999). Among these factors, it is widely recognized that soil organisms, especially soil macrofauna and microorganisms play an important role in maintaining soil structural stability (Erktan et al., 2022). However, their exact contribution is unclear and requires further research. In order to assess the link between soil structure maintenance and soil organisms, a study was conducted using data from MINOTAUR field campaign carried on 9 long Term Experimental (LTE) sites. These LTE are located in 8 European countries: Austria (BOKU), Spain (INIA), France (ACO1), Italy (CREA), the Netherlands (WUR), Switzerland (AGS), Sweden (SLU1 and SLU2), and Slovenia (ULBF), representing a diverse range of soil and climatic conditions, as well as different geographical contexts. All sites have been established for at least ten years, featuring crop rotations predominantly focused on cereals. The agricultural practices include varying combinations of fertilization techniques and soil tillage methods (Aponte et al., 2024).

Soil aggregate stability was measured using Le Bissonnais method (1996) which is based on 3 tests reflecting 3 environmental constraints: i) fast wetting, reflecting the effect of heavy rain or irrigation, ii) slow wetting, reflecting the effect of light rain, iii) mechanical breakdown by shaking reflecting raindrop impact on a wet soil mimic erosion caused by torrential rainfall or mechanical pressure (Péres et al., 2013). By employing these complementary tests, the project can explore not only the general mechanisms behind soil stabilization but also how specific soil properties and biological factors respond differently to various forms of water-induced stress. The results will reveal how soil structural stability varies depending on biological and physicochemical parameters, providing insights into the resilience of soils under diverse environmental conditions.

As earthworm and microorganisms are widely recognized to play an important role in maintaining soil structural stability (Erktan et al., 2022), we focused our attention on these two groups. Microorganisms were characterized in term of microbial biomass, fungal and bacterial biomass. Earthworm communities were sampled by hand sorting method (20 cm * 20 cm) completed with mustard application in the hole (500 ml). They were characterized by global metrics (abundance and biomass) and their ecological groups (Bouché, 1977; Lee, 1985): i) epigeic species live in the litter and produce casts at the soil surface that affect its roughness and the distribution of macropores, ii) anecic species live in vertical burrows, used as shelters and connected with the soil surface, iii) endogeic species make horizontal or randomly oriented burrows in the mineral soil, considered as temporary structures because they are rarely re-used. In

complement, based on specific actions of anecic on soil structuration, in relation to their different feeding activity, this ecological group was subdivided in two sub-group: epi-anecic, linked to *Lumbricus* species, and strict-anecic, linked to *Aporrectodea* species (Hoeffner et al., 2022).

At the end, a large dataset of parameters was used to explain the aggregate stability values (table 1).

Table 1: List of studied parameters in the analysis of aggregate stability

	Studied parameter	Metrics
Aggregate stability	Structural stability (MWD)	mm
Biological parameters	Earthworm abundance	ind.m ⁻²
	Earthworm biomass	g.m ⁻²
	Epigeic biomass	g.m ⁻²
	Epigeic abundance	ind.m ⁻²
	Epi-Anecic biomass	g.m ⁻²
	Epi-Anecic abundance	ind.m ⁻²
	Strict- Anecic abundance	ind.m ⁻²
	Strict- Anecic biomass	g.m ⁻²
	Total Anecic biomass	g.m ⁻²
	Endogeic biomass	g.m ⁻²
	Endogeic abundance	ind.m ⁻²
	Bacterial biomass	nmol FAME g ⁻¹ soil
	Fungal biomass	nmol FAME g ⁻¹ soil
	Microbial biomass	nmol FAME g ⁻¹ soil
Climatic parameters	Temperature	°C
	Precipitation	mm by year
Physico-chemical parameters	Soil moisture	%
	pH H ₂ O	
	Mineral element (Al, Ca, Cu, Fe, Ca, K, Mg, Mn, Ni, P, Pb, Zn, Cr)	%
	Organic Carbon	%
	Total Carbon	%
	Texture	% of sand, silt and clay
Agronomical parameters	Tillage treatment	ST (superficial tillage) / CT (conventional tillage) / DS (direct seeding)
	Tillage depth	Mm
	Fertilization	OG (organic) / MN (mineral) / NF (non)
	Crop rotation	Names
	Cover crop	Names
	Pesticide use	Yes or No

Statistical tools. Statistical analyses were performed using R software version 4.3.2. An Excel file consolidates all data, including tested parameters and structural stability values. The summary table is organized with each row representing an MWD value tested under different locations and conditions. In the initial analysis, descriptive statistics and structural stability values were calculated and compared across locations, test types or agronomical modalities. Statistical significance of observed differences was assessed using ANOVA tests. Pairwise comparisons were conducted when significant differences were detected. Correlation matrices were computed to quantify relationships between variables, with coefficients (Pearson coefficient) used to highlight significant correlations (the limit of -0.35 and 0.35 was arbitrary proposed). We performed Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to reduce the dimensionality of the dataset and eliminate parameters with low contribution to the overall variability. The MWD was then modeled using a linear model (GLM). Model assumptions were verified, including normality (Shapiro-Wilk test > 5%) and homoscedasticity (Levene's test > 5%). The model's performance was assessed using root mean square error (RMSE) and adjusted R² to ensure a robust fit. The MWD served as the dependent variable, while explanatory variables included experimental conditions and site characteristics.

Results: the maintenance of soil structure by the process of aggregation of particles into soil aggregates

is shown to be promoted by a range of soil organisms: microorganisms as well as earthworms act positively on aggregate stability. The analysis of abiotic and biotic factors shows that i) considering the microbial component, microbial biomass and bacterial biomass are good predictors of aggregate stability, ii) considering earthworm community, earthworm biomass, more than earthworm density, is a good predictor of aggregate stability, as well as anecic biomass and to some extent endogeic biomass, while epigeic biomass is not a good predictor. The study also shows that the biological predictors can be different depending on the aggregate stability test used: while the epi-anecic (i.e. *Lumbricus* species) is a good predictor whatever the test, the strict-anecic (i.e. *Aporrectodea* species) turned out as a good predictor only when the slow-wetting test was used. These differences reinforce the interest to assess soil aggregate stability by different tests, which could be defined as “functional” tests.

In synthesis, using data from the 9 LTE assessed in MINOTAUR, the study showed that agricultural practices have a moderate role in aggregate stability, while soil biodiversity emerged as a key determinant of soil aggregate stability, with certain microbial and faunal groups demonstrating significant influence. Bacteria, through their production of extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) and their role in organic matter dynamics, were consistently correlated with higher stability across all tests. Similarly, the epi-anecic earthworm group significantly enhanced stability through deep bioturbation and organic matter processing. However, fungi only showed a moderate correlation, with comparatively less impact on soil stability in this study.

Perspectives:

- A manuscript, based on MINOTAUR data, is in preparation and will be submitted in 2025.
- The robustness of these results will be tested by increasing the data set, including data from other international projects, such as SoilMan (BioDiversa) and SUSTAIN (SNOWMAN). The data compilation started during MINOTAUR project but faced different issues such as the absence of environmental data (soil properties, agricultural practices) or the heterogeneity of measurement methods.
- The 5 classes of erosion risk (from low to high risk) proposed by Le Bissonais 1996 could be used to define some threshold values in order to quantify functional relationships and specify the Ecological Production Function.

4. Water regulation - Infiltration

Water infiltration is a major process in soil functioning and soil health as it contributes to groundwater recharge, it has a major importance to the amount of water available within the soil for plant and by consequence primary production, it limits ponding which results in reduced oxygen availability and reduced nutrient cycling, it guarantees the moisture retention. Moreover, it decreases the risk of runoff and prevents erosion.

In order to assess the link between water infiltration and soil organisms, a study was conducted using data from MINOTAUR field campaign carried on 9 long Term Experimental (LTE) sites (cf part 2 for the description). Considering the main effect of macrofauna on soil macroporosity and by consequence on water infiltration (Blouin et al., 2013 ; Spurgeon et al., 2013), this study focusses on the relationships between earthworms community structure and infiltration, with the following questions: i) what are good earthworm community predictors of water infiltration in the field ? ii) what is the quantitative contribution of earthworms to water infiltration?

Water infiltration was measured using Beerkan method (ring method - saturated hydraulic conductivity, K_{sat} mm.h⁻¹). Earthworm communities were sampled by hand sorting method (20 cm * 20 cm) completed with mustard application in the hole (500 ml). As for aggregate stability assessment, they were characterized by global metrics (abundance and biomass) and their ecological groups (Bouché, 1977; Lee, 1985): epigeic, endogeic and anecic, with the subdivision in two sub-groups: epi-anecic, linked to *Lumbricus* species, and strict-anecic, linked to *Aporrectodea* species (Hoeffner et al., 2022). Moreover, they were also characterized by functional groups: burrower (epi-anecic), litter dweller (epigeic), shallow bioturbator (epi-endogeic), intense tunneler (anecic), deep bioturbator (hypo-endogeic) (Capowiez et al.,

2024). In addition, the communities were characterized by taxonomic and functional diversity indices.

At the end, a large dataset of biotic and abiotic parameters was used to explain the infiltration values (table 2).

Table 2: List of studied parameters in the analysis of water infiltration

	Studied parameter	Metrics
Infiltration rate	Saturated hydraulic conductivity (Ksat)	mm.h ⁻¹
Biological parameters	Earthworm abundance	ind.m ⁻²
	Epigeic abundance	ind.m ⁻²
	Epi-Anecic abundance	ind.m ⁻²
	Strict- Anecic abundance	ind.m ⁻²
	Total Anecic abundance	ind.m ⁻²
	Endogeic abundance	ind.m ⁻²
	Burrowers abundance	ind.m ⁻²
	Litter dweller abundance	ind.m ⁻²
	shallow bioturbator abundance	ind.m ⁻²
	intense tunneler abundance	ind.m ⁻²
	deep bioturbator abundance	ind.m ⁻²
Climatic parameters	Temperature (mean annual)	°C
	Precipitation (mean annual)	mm
	pH H ₂ O	
	Organic Carbon	%
	Total Carbon	%
	Texture	% of sand, silt and clay

Statistical tool: correlation matrix and models were applied to identify the predictor (the limit of -0.35 and 0.35 was arbitrary proposed to identify the predictor) of infiltration and quantifying functional relationships.

Results: the study showed that within abiotic soil parameters, organic carbon is the only one which is correlated with infiltration. Earthworm community diversity descriptors (taxonomic or functional richness and diversity) could be defined as predictors of water infiltration, as well as anecic abundance considering as total anecic abundance or epi-anecic and strict anecic abundance. Regarding functional groups, the intense tunnellers could also be considered as predictor (Table 3).

In synthesis: soil water regulation in terms of water infiltration rate is shown to be substantially enhanced by earthworms. The species composition of the earthworm community is shown to be particularly relevant, and some species can help to prevent or mitigate deleterious effects of heavy downpour events more than others. Here, differences between species in behavioral traits in feeding and burrowing, as well as the sizes of their populations drive the process of soil bioturbation. The mitigation of soil surface crusting promotes infiltration, and the burrows of anecic species can provide preferential flow paths for infiltrating water.

Perspective:

- A manuscript, based on MINOTAUR data, is in preparation and will be submitted in 2025.
- The robustness of these results will be tested by increasing the data set, including data from other international projects, such as EcoFinders, SoilMan and SoilServ. The data compilation started during MINOTAUR project but faced different issues such as the absence of environmental data (soil properties, agricultural practices).
- Based on the bigger dataset, the quantifying of the functional relationships will be improved in order to specify the Ecological Production Function and define the quantitative contribution of earthworms to water infiltration.

5. Carbon sequestration

Carbon sequestration is one of the major pillars of soil health in the context of climate change, and carbon loss is identified by the EU Soil Monitoring Law as a major risk of soil degradation (EC 2023). It is recognised that soil organic carbon levels increase through the subsequent stabilization of microbial necromass (Liang et al. 2019). If not stabilized, the breakdown of microbial tissue carbon is potentially returned to the atmosphere. A higher C_{mic}/SOC ratio indicates a better efficiency of microorganism in converting C sources into microbial biomass. The proposed C_{mic}/SOC threshold is 2.2%, representing equilibrium between C mineralization (respiration) and sequestration (Jenkinson and Ladd, 1981; Anderson and Domsch 1989).

The topic of this study is the carbon sequestration in relation to microbial biomass. The question which is addressed is about the relevancy of using the ratio between microbial biomass-C and soil organic carbon to assess carbon sequestration. Here, the effect of tillage practices is investigated to show that reduced intensity of tillage may promote fungi and their increased biomass effectively can enhance SOC. The study is based on data from 23 experiments including 9 LTE involved in MINOTAUR (see description part 2) (Aponte et al., 2024) with additional sites from different countries. The LTE durations are from 3 years to 45 years, with for some of them several sampling time which allows to assess the robustness of the results over time. Data analysis is under progress due to issues collecting data.

6. Synthesis

The table 3, shows a list of the different predictors which can be considered when assessing primary production (Romero et al., 2024), soil structure maintenance (aggregate stability) and water regulation (infiltration).

Table 3: Synthesis of main predictors of Primary production (from Romero et al., 2024), soil structure maintenance, water regulation.
 In green: predictor with positive effect; in Orange: predictors with negative effect; in white: no information; NS: no significant; ‘-’: predictor not part of the top ten predictors; NA: not analysed predictor; $0.35 < X < -0.35$: arbitrary limits defined in the correlation matrix.

		Primary productivity (Random Forest)			Primary productivity (SEM)			Soil structure maintenance (correlation matrix)	Water regulation (correlation matrix)
		Fraction of absorbed photosynthetic active radiation (FAPAR)			Fraction of absorbed photosynthetic active radiation (FAPAR)			Aggregate stability (MWD, mm)	Infiltration (mm/h)
		arableland/cropland	grassland	forest/woodland	arableland/cropland	grassland	forest/woodland		
Climate	Temperature		NS					$0.35 < x < -0.35$	
	Precipitation		NS					$0.35 < x < -0.35$	
Practices	Tillage depth	NA	NA	NA			$0.35 < x < -0.35$	NA	
Soil properties	pH			NS				$0.35 < x < -0.35$	
	Clay content	-	-					$0.35 < x < -0.35$	
	Soil Density	-	-				NA	NA	
	Soil organic carbon								
	Phosphorus content		-	-				NA	NA
	Soil moisture	NA	NA	NA				$0.35 < x < -0.35$	NA
Microbial component	Microbial biomass	-	NS					NA	
	Bacterial biomass	NA	NA	NA				$0.35 < x < -0.35$	
	Fungi biomass	NA	NA	NA				NA	
	Acidobacteria		NS	-				NA	NA
	Firmicutes		-					NA	NA
	Proteobacteria			-				NA	NA
	Actinobacteria		-	-				NA	NA
	Verrucomicrobia	NS	NS	NS				NA	NA
	Mycorrhiza	-		-				NA	NA
	Basidiomycota	-	NS	-				NA	NA
	Chytridiomycota	NI	NI	NI				NA	NA
	Plant pathogens	-	-	NS				NA	NA
Earthworm community	Earthworm abundance	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	$0.35 < x < -0.35$	
	Earthworm biomass	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
	Epigeic biomass	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	$0.35 < x < -0.35$	
	Epigeic abundance	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	$0.35 < x < -0.35$	
	Epi-Anecic biomass	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
	Epi-Anecic abundance	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
	Strict- Anecic abundance	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
	Strict- Anecic biomass	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
	Total Anecic abundance	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
	Endogeic biomass	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
	Endogeic abundance	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	$0.35 < x < -0.35$	
	Earthworm- Species richness	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
	Earthworm- Species diversity	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
	Earthworm - Functional richness	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
	Earthworm - Functional diversity	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
	Intense Burrowers	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	$0.35 < x < -0.35$	
	Intense Tunnelers	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
Shallow bioturbators	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	$0.35 < x < -0.35$		
Litter dwellers	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	$0.35 < x < -0.35$		
Intermediaite	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	$0.35 < x < -0.35$		

7. Perspectives

While the MINOTAUR project has closed to date, it is the ambition of the authors to publish the results of this particular study in a peer-reviewed journal. This has already been done for one ecosystem service (primary production, Romero et al., 2024), but not for the others. As such, publication would appear under its own DOI, the raw data used in the analyses will be published as supplementary information in the journal, and to avoid further duplication are not available in association to this Zenodo deposited document. When published, the DOI of the paper will be provided here in an update.

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